

Appendix

Visually Retracing and Comparing Filter Steps in Exploratory Process Mining

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Appendix contents: The following material provides additional information for **Section 6 (Evaluation)** of the paper “*Visually Retracing and Comparing Filter Steps in Exploratory Process Mining*”. It includes the detailed interview protocol, an overview of the study participants, the qualitative coding scheme used for analyzing the interview data, and the detailed results of the ICE-T questionnaire.

1 Interview Protocol

In addition to the think-aloud protocol and quantitative measures, several open-ended questions were asked to gather qualitative feedback. The questions were grouped into two thematic categories:

1. **Implementation of the Approach** These questions focused on how participants perceived the functionality and usability of the prototype.
 - **Q1a:** Which features of the artifact were most informative or useful, and which were not?
 - **Q1b:** Which additional features would better support analysis?
2. **Use in Practice** These questions focused on how participants envisioned using the artifact in real-world analytical contexts.
 - **Q2a:** At which points during your analysis process would you consider using the artifact, and why?
 - **Q2b:** Could you think of a real-world task or project where the artifact would be useful? How would you integrate it into your workflow?

During the sessions, participants were also asked follow-up questions to clarify their comments during the think-aloud phase. For example, if a participant said “this is confusing” or “this is nice”, the interviewer asked them to specify which

element they were referring to. This allowed us to better understand the reasons behind participants’ reactions.

Before filling out the ICE-T questionnaire, participants were informed that they could elaborate on their responses if they wished. For example, if they indicated that the artifact supported certain analysis tasks particularly well, they were invited to explain why they believed the artifact performed well in that respect. This possibility to elaborate on questionnaire responses was communicated beforehand to encourage richer qualitative feedback.

2 Overview of Participants

Table 1. Overview of the study participants. The Table reports the participants’ position, location, process mining experience in years (PM Exp) and self-reported expertise.

ID	Position	Country	PM Exp.	Expertise
P1	PhD Student	Germany	5 years	Average
P2	Assistant Professor	Netherlands	8 years	Advanced
P3	Senior Researcher	Switzerland	2 years	Basic
P4	PhD Student	Chile	4.5 years	Advanced
P5	PhD Student	Chile	4 years	Good
P6	PhD Student	Netherlands	1 year	Basic
P7	Product Owner	Germany	5 years	Good
P8	ICT Developer	Netherlands	2 years	Good
P9	PhD Student	Spain	5 years	Average

3 Coding Scheme

The think-aloud and interview were inductively open-coded to capture reflective segments in which participants discussed their experience with the artifact. The resulting codes were subsequently grouped into three categories reflecting design requirements (DR1, DR2, DR3). Segments that did not directly correspond to these requirements were retained as additional themes. The table below presents the final coding scheme together with example statements, the frequency (Freq.), and the number of total participants supporting a given theme (#P).

Table 2. Coding scheme with example statements

Category	Description	Example Statement	Freq.	#P
DR1	Participants recognized and appreciated the ability to retrace applied filtering steps and understand how intermediate results were obtained.	<p>“I think I really like that path where you can see how the filters are connected and ... see how it differs between different filter options.” (P2)</p> <p>“It’s the different parts because you can follow and trace the different outcomes ... very useful for identifying the different ways.” (P8)</p> <p>“... sometimes it’s very difficult to remember the filters that you have applied before ... very useful to follow your analysis and understand why the results ... are related with the previous one.” (P7)</p>	20	6
DR2	Participants appreciated the possibility to compare results across different filtering paths and identify differences between groups of cases.	<p>“So you can see I’m comparing the tails, the different results, so they are relevant.” (P8)</p> <p>“It was interesting to compare these two sets ... seeing that information was really useful.” (P5)</p> <p>“I think it is very effective as representation because it is inherently showing you partitions. So you can see what is related ... and also by difference.” (P4)</p>	14	8
DR3	Participants recognized and valued the possibility to analyze the filtered results through multiple analytical perspectives and metrics.	<p>“The visualisation shows multiple perspectives of the data. ... I would have liked to see even more metrics.” (P5)</p> <p>“I actually have multiple perspectives ... the data perspective and also the process perspective.” (P3)</p> <p>“They do show multiple perspectives. I like the fact that there is also hovering information ... this goes beyond what I can see in the chart.” (P4)</p>	13	8
AT	Additional themes capturing reflections not directly linked to the design requirements.	<p>“In the very beginning, when you are just exploring your data set, I think this is quite a useful tool ... because it gives you an intuitive view of the data.” (P9)</p> <p>“This visualisation provides a strong point of entry to do these kinds of exploration.” (P6)</p> <p>“To be honest, it’s great to give a quick overview at a glance.” (P7)</p> <p>“If you want to look at the bigger picture ... this is also something nice.” (P10)</p>	58	9

4 Detailed ICE-T Results

This section provides the detailed results of the ICE-T questionnaire [1] collected during the evaluation. The questionnaire evaluates visualizations across four dimensions: Insight, Confidence, Essence, and Time.

Fig. 1. Detailed results of the ICE-T questionnaire across all participants.

References

1. Emily Wall, Meeshu Agnihotri, Laura Matzen, Kristin Divis, Michael Haass, Alex Endert, and John Stasko. A heuristic approach to value-driven evaluation of visualizations. *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics*, 25(1):491–500, 2018.